

Enhancing Nursing Knowledge and Skills to Support Quality Improvement in Primary Health Care Services

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Abstract

Background: Enhancing the quality-of-care nurses deliver by focusing on training and continuous professional development programs is a critical issue in nursing.

Aim: To evaluate the impact of training programs on nurses' professional development regarding knowledge, skills, and attitudes toward patient care.

Method: A Descriptive design conducted by the Nursing education for nursing staff as part of their training portfolio. Program and pre & post tests given (*Blood extraction & ECG for 35 Nurses*) (*Med. Calculation for 39 Nurses*).

Result: Training programs significantly impact nurses' professional development in Blood extraction and Med. calculation towards patient care. The mean scores for the post-training survey were significantly higher than the mean scores for the pre-training survey.

Conclusion: Training programs had a positive impact on nurses' professional development.

More Information

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Keywords:

Training programs, professional development, blood extraction & Medication calculation, patient care, healthcare service delivery, and patient outcomes.

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Introduction

The primary healthcare system is the cornerstone of effective healthcare delivery, emphasizing prevention, early intervention, and management of chronic conditions. Nurses, as integral members of the healthcare team, play a pivotal role in ensuring the quality of care through direct patient interaction, care coordination, and patient education [1,2]. Enhancing their knowledge and skills is essential to support quality improvement initiatives that aim to improve care processes and patient outcomes [3].

Implementing quality improvement programs in primary health care is essential to enhance the efficiency, effectiveness, and patient-centeredness of care. Such programs aim to systematically improve healthcare processes and outcomes through the adoption of best practices, data-driven decision-making, and continuous evaluation. However, barriers

such as inadequate staffing, lack of quality improvement training, and resistance to change often impede progress. A qualitative scoping review study identified the need for stronger institutional support and better integration of quality improvement training into regular nursing practice [1].

Another pilot study conducted by Fitzpatrick et al. reported that engaging nurses in research and quality improvement is associated with higher job satisfaction and lower rates of unscheduled time off work [4]. A systematic review study showed the effectiveness of RNs on patient outcomes in primary care, specifically concerning satisfaction, enablement, quality of life, self-efficacy, and improvements in health behaviors [2]. Ongoing evaluation that accounts for primary care register nurses' unique scope of practice and emphasizes the patient experience is necessary to optimize the delivery of patient-centered primary care.

Researches show that nurses are uniquely positioned to contribute to quality improvement in primary care due to their close contact with patients and their ability to observe and address care gaps [2,5,6]. A Systematic Review study highlighted that nurse-led interventions in chronic disease management significantly reduced hospital admissions and improved patient compliance with treatment regimens [7]. The study conducted by Hickey, and Giardino, reported that nurses who understand the processes of care including what works well and what does not, and they have the clinical experience and scientific knowledge needed to improving processes of care that lead to more effective patient outcomes [3].

To be effective in quality improvement, nurses need a combination of clinical expertise and an understanding of quality improvement methodologies [5]. The Institute of Medicine (IOM) identified core competencies such as the ability to apply evidence-based practices, use quality improvement tools, and engage in interdisciplinary teamwork. A qualitative descriptive study found that nurses with quality improvement training were more confident in using data to identify problems and implement changes [8]. A meta-analysis study found that nurses trained in QI methods and chronic disease management were able to reduce hospital readmissions by up to 15% [9]. Similarly, a cross-sectional Study reported that patient satisfaction scores improved when nurses engaged in structured communication and patient education programs [10]. While a descriptive, cross-sectional study revealed that most of the patients were highly satisfied with the overall quality of hospital care and care provided by the nurse [6].

Educational strategies are considered as a corn stone to enhance nursing knowledge and skills. Evidence supports the use of continuing education, simulation training, and structured mentorship programs that have good effectiveness in improving the nursing quality of care provided to the patients. In the study that developed an approachable simulation for teams of health care trainees at any level and any discipline reported that continuing education programs focused on quality improvement principles significantly improved nurses' ability to participate in and lead quality improvement projects [11]. Simulation training, as reviewed by a descriptive study based on searched and used literature data, helps nurses practice critical skills in a risk-free environment, enhancing their readiness for real-world challenges [12]. Another descriptive qualitative study reported that continuous education and training enable nurses to become leaders in best practices, contribute to innovation, and play an important role in improving the quality of health care [13].

Empirical studies consistently show that enhancing nursing skills leads to better patient care outcomes. For example, A systematic review study revealed that nursing interventions had a significant impact on improving patient outcomes. Interventions such as patient education, medication management, infection control, pain management, wound care management, and fall prevention were found to be effective across different healthcare settings [7].

Study Question

How do training programs impact nursing performance regarding knowledge, skills, and attitudes toward patient care?

Aim of the Study

To evaluate the impact of training programs on nurses' professional development regarding knowledge, skills, and attitudes towards patient care.

Methods

This study evaluates the effectiveness of specific training programs conducted for nursing staff, focusing on blood extraction, ECG, and medication calculations. It aims to analyze pre-and post-test scores to determine knowledge and skill improvements among the participants.

A total of 39 nurses participated in the medication calculations program, while 35 nurses underwent training in blood extraction and ECG. The training included theoretical instruction and practical demonstrations, followed by assessments to measure competency.

Results

Figure 1 shows that training programs significantly impact nurses' professional development in Blood extraction toward patient care. The mean scores for the pre-tests (5.4 for blood extraction) and post-training surveys were compared to the extent of the improvement (8.7 for blood extraction).

Figure 2 shows that training programs have a significant impact on nurses' professional development in ECG toward patient care. The mean scores for the pre-tests (2.84 for ECG) and post-training surveys were compared to the extent of the improvement (4.45 for post-ECG test)

Figure 3 shows the study found that training programs have a significant impact on nurses' professional development in medication calculation and that impact on patient care.

The mean scores for the pre-tests (13.5 For Medication Calculation) and post-training surveys were compared to the extent of the improvement (16.5 For Medication Calculation) indicating that the mean scores for the post-training survey were significantly higher than the mean scores for the pre-training survey.

Figure 1 .SN3 Blood Extraction Score For Pre & Post Training Of Nursing Staff

Figure 2. SN3 ECG Score For Pre & Post Training Of Nursing Staff

Figure 3.SN1 & SN2 Medication calculation Score pre-post training of nursing staff

Conclusion

The findings revealed that training programs had a positive impact on nurses' professional development. Nurses reported that the training programs provided them with new knowledge, skills, and strategies to manage patients effectively. They also reported that the training enhanced their critical thinking,

communication, and teamwork skills, leading to improved patient outcomes. Furthermore, the nurses indicated that the training programs positively influenced their attitudes toward patient care.

The study affirms the importance of training programs in promoting nurses' professional development in terms of knowledge, skills, and attitudes towards

patient care. The findings from the study indicate that training programs have a positive impact on nurses' performance, leading to improved patient outcomes. Therefore, hospitals should invest in training programs to enhance nurses' knowledge, skills, and attitudes toward patient care, leading to improved healthcare service delivery and patient outcomes.

Recommendation

There is a need to invest in training programs that are tailored to meet nurses' needs to improve their knowledge and skills in patient care. Also, to incorporate training programs into their staff development plans to ensure that all nurses have access to regular training. Also, there is a need for continuous evaluation of the impact of training programs on nurses' professional development regularly. And Hospitals should create a positive work environment that encourages nurses to apply the knowledge, and skills gained from training programs. And overall, there is a need for further research to investigate the long-term impact of training programs on nurses' professional development and patient outcomes. In conclusion, with a continuous investment in nurses' professional development through training programs, healthcare quality and patient safety can be improved.

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